

Mosaic Immersion: Stacked Realities Merging Physical and Virtual Experiences

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ABSTRACT

The *Mosaic Immersion* is a mixed-reality installation that reimagines the ancient practice of cairn stacking for the digital age. Within an augmented reality space, participants create and interact with virtual rocks featuring their unique hand movement scans, each embodying personal narratives. Inspired by the cultural significance of trail cairns as symbols of guidance and connection, the installation transforms rock stacking into a communal, contemplative virtual experience. Participants contribute to or observe a growing virtual cairn, exploring themes of resilience and human connection. This immersive journey blurs the boundaries between physical and virtual worlds, inviting reflection on shared experiences and collective memory in our increasingly digital world.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Applied computing → Media Arts • Human-centered computing → Human-computer interaction (HCI) → Interaction paradigms → Augmented reality

KEYWORDS

Mixed Reality Art Installation, Augmented Reality, Embodied Interaction, Shared Narratives

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1 Introduction

The concept of *Mosaic Immersion* installation draws inspiration from the ancient practice of cairn stacking. Cairns, created by carefully balancing rocks on top of one another, serve as markers or symbols that guide and connect hikers. This practice holds both cultural and personal significance, transforming the deliberate act of arranging stones into a ceremonial and contemplative activity. Cairns can serve as forms of self-expression, ways to leave messages for others, prayers for the well-being of loved ones, or gestures of each

rock in a cairn embodies the collective essence of countless individuals—their time, stories, interactions, warmth, and histories woven together. These rock formations foster a communal experience, encouraging others to add their stones to the collective effort or to simply appreciate the shared creation.

The *Mosaic Immersion* installation merges the tangible act of rock stacking with immersive augmented reality, inviting participants on a transformative journey where personal narratives come together into a shared mosaic of experiences. In this environment, participants generate unique rocks featuring their own hand textures and record their voices to share personal stories. Using VR controllers, they can grab these personalized rocks and place them within an augmented space that incorporates tree stump fixtures. The installation not only allows for individual expression but also fosters a sense of community, as participants can listen to the stories shared by others. This interactive approach creates a deeply personal yet shared experience, where each rock with a story becomes part of a larger, collective narrative, much like the cairns that have long served as markers of human presence and connection in nature.

2 Background

2.1 Personal Inspiration from Korean Stone Stacking Ritual

Rock stacking rituals, deeply rooted in many cultures worldwide, hold a particularly significant place in Korean traditions, manifesting in various forms that reflect the intersection of spirituality, community, and nature. Two notable expressions of this practice in Korea are the Tapje ritual and mountain stone stacking. These traditions have directly influenced to the project.

The Tapje ritual, performed during Seol (Lunar New Year), is a community ceremony where villagers construct conical stone stacks at the village entrance. These meticulously assembled structures, often in male-female pairs, serve as guardian deities and low shrines. Aligned with geomantic principles, they

transform simple stones into powerful symbols of collective devotion and hope. The ritual involves prayers, incense burning, and candle lighting, binding the community together through shared spiritual beliefs and connection to their surroundings [1].

In contrast, mountain stone stacking is a more individualized practice, particularly prevalent in spiritually significant areas like Gyeryong Mountain in Korea. These varied stone piles represent personal hopes and wishes, with each added stone symbolizing a prayer or aspiration. Common wishes include health and success for children, especially those facing important life events like college entrance. The act of adding to existing piles highlights the interconnectedness of human desires and the belief that communal support strengthens individual wishes. This practice embodies the Korean philosophy that good deeds and kindness towards others bring blessings to oneself and future generations, reinforcing the idea of cosmic reciprocity in human actions and intentions.

Both traditions demonstrate how the simple act of stacking stones can evolve into profound expressions of faith, community, and the human connection to the natural world, serving as tangible reminders of the power of collective and individual spiritual practices in Korean culture.

2.2 Embodied Immersion

Through the *Mosaic Immersion* installation, the artists explore the concept of immersion. The concept of immersion is traditionally understood as the phenomenon where viewers become so engrossed in a virtual environment that the real-world fades away, replaced by a computationally created realm of imagination [2]. Embodied immersion, a concept emphasizing deep multisensory engagement and physical presence in experiences where the body movement becomes an integral part of the interaction and perception process [3]. In the context of the *Mosaic Immersion* project, embodied immersion can play a crucial role in enhancing the participants' experience and connection to the stone stacking ritual [4, 5].

The collective bodily experience of observing and participating alongside others cultivates embodied empathy, strengthening the communal aspect of the ritual. Furthermore, by mimicking the physical gestures of traditional stone stacking, participants embody the ritual in a technologically enhanced way. This multifaceted sensory engagement not only leads to stronger memory formation but also deepens participants' connection to the stone stacking tradition, their personal narratives, and the collective story being constructed.

3 Interaction Design

3.1 Augmented Space Design

The installation is equipped with several key elements. These include a custom-made hand scanning box for capturing hand

movements, a computer system to process and manage the virtual assets, tree stump like objects for users to stack virtual rocks in the augmented environment and an area designated for two to three participants to use Meta Quest 3 headsets simultaneously.

To enhance the experience for observers and create a more inclusive atmosphere, a projection system displays the virtual environment to the wider audience. Physical tree stump props are strategically placed throughout the space, adding tactile elements that bridge the digital and natural worlds (Figure 1).

Figure 1: *Mosaic Immersion*'s physical space (top) and an augmented space through the virtual reality headset (bottom)

3.2 User Experience Design

Participants enter the installation space with their Meta Quest 3 headsets. The headset's passthrough mode allows participants to navigate the space while maintaining visual awareness of their surroundings and fellow participants, creating an augmented experience. Participants can create virtual rocks decorated with unique textures by inserting their hands into the white hand-capturing box while wearing the headsets. The experience deepens as participants are invited to imbue their rocks with personal narratives, guided by thought-provoking prompts such as, "Describe a place that holds special meaning for you." As they speak, their words are captured, becoming an integral part of their virtual rock. This process of creation and storytelling encourages reflection and fosters a sense of connection to the digital artifact. Participants can then interact with these rocks, grasping them to listen to the narratives.

This harmonious blend of past and present, physical and virtual, personal and collective, creates a truly immersive journey of self-discovery and shared human connection.

Figure 2. User experience procedure: 1) Participant captures hand movements in the box, 2) Capture preview screen, 3) Audio recording screen, 4) The system generates a rock with the participant's hand textures, and 5) the newly generated rock appears on the pedestal where participants can pick up the stone to listen to the recorded audio.

4 Technical Details

4.1 Installation Setup

Figure 3 illustrates the layout for the Mosaic Immersion installation, which spans 5 meters in width and 3 meters in depth. At the forefront of the setup is a projection screen spanning the width of the space, providing an observer's view in the space. The strategic placement of the elements of the project suggests a flow that participants might follow: from receiving headsets, engaging with the hand-capturing box, and then fully immersing themselves in the interactive experience facilitated by the tree stump props and projection screen.

Figure 3: Installation layout

The system overview diagram (Figure 4) for Mosaic Immersion outlines the data flow and connectivity between the physical components used by participants and the software that processes and synchronizes the virtual experience.

Figure 4: System overview diagram

4.2 Capturing Animated Hands

The hand-capturing box is designed to capture the dynamic hand motions of participants using motion capture, chroma key compositing, and real-time video techniques. It employs TouchDesigner [6], Unity [7], and a webcam to achieve this. Here's how it works: the webcam captures live video and feeds it into TouchDesigner, where motion is detected and captured. Upon capturing, the TouchDesigner script applies chroma keying and digital masking, mirroring the image to create intriguing visuals. These manipulated images are then processed in Unity to generate unique hand textures of rocks (Figure 5). The resulting live feed snapshots are saved as animated GIFs on the local computer (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Dynamic hand-capturing process within TouchDesigner

Figure 6: Captured animated hands

4.3 Rock Generation System

Each virtual rock in the installation consists of both visual and auditory components. The Unity project runs a file system watcher on the main computer which handles any GIF files created by the TouchDesigner process. When a new file is created, the Unity process uploads the GIF to an asset server and instructs client VR headsets to download the new GIF file. The frames of this GIF file are extracted into a list of 2D textures, which are used as the albedo texture for the spawned rocks; a script animates the texture by rotating through those frames. The shape of each rock is determined by selecting from a variety of pre-designed low poly meshes, allowing for diversity in their appearance. Audio is recorded directly on the VR headsets through a user interface located above the physical hand-capturing box in the virtual space. This is saved as a WAV file and uploaded to the asset server on the main computer, which then instructs other client VR headsets to download the WAV file so that it is available for replay. To maintain a cohesive link between the visual and auditory elements of each rock, a Globally Unique Identifier (GUID) is assigned. This ensures that the textures, audio, and chosen mesh, along with any relevant metadata, remain interconnected within the system, preserving the integrity and uniqueness of each rock's story and appearance.

Figure 7: Virtual rocks generated by participants

4.4 Development of Augmented Reality Space

Using the Meta XR SDK [8], it implements Passthrough AR, while the Depth API [9] ensures dynamic occlusion, prioritizing physical objects over virtual ones. The Scene API [10] aligns virtual physics with real-world objects, enhancing intuitive interactions. Synchronization across devices is achieved through the Photon Fusion networking library [11], ensuring consistent rock placement and physics across all headsets. To fine-tune alignment, users can manually adjust the virtual environment using controller triggers. The UI for creating rocks is shared between all headsets via the networking library so that other users in the space can watch the rock creation process even if they are not the one creating it.

5 Participants' Experiences

It was observed that the user experience in the *Mosaic Immersion* installation was intuitive, engaging, and immersive, despite some difficulties with VR controllers among participants who had never used VR before. Participants often repeated the hand scanning process multiple times to achieve more distinctive animations of their hands, frequently looking for recognizable characteristics such as rings or watches. They also shared a wide range of personal memories. The stories varied, with many participants reminiscing about their childhoods with siblings, parents, children, and friends. These narratives were cheerful, filled with smiles, and heartwarming, creating a deeply emotional and communal experience for all involved.

6 Conclusion

The *Mosaic Immersion* embodies human touch and narrative within an augmented space, highlighting the human connection and expression. This installation serves as a bridge between the tradition of cairn stacking and digital interaction techniques. As participants leave their digital marks, they don't just leave behind a rock; they leave a story, a piece of themselves that is woven into a collective memory. The technological aspects of the project, from hand motion capture to audio recording, have facilitated this process and elevated the participants' experience, creating a blend of the real and the virtual.

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